

IMPLEMENTING A SUITE OF SKILLS MODULES IN A FIRST-YEAR ENGINEERING PROJECT-BASED SUBJECT

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ABSTRACT

Students commencing engineering at university often have no prior experience of engineering, what the profession entails and the distinctions between disciplines. Consequently, tertiary institutions often offer common first-year engineering subjects that aim to give students an experience of the engineering profession and method, while providing exposure to different disciplines through applied project-based learning. The difficulty with this approach is that there is a wide variance in terms of students' knowledge, skills, past experiences, and expectations. In a team context, these discrepancies could lead to conflict and poor educational outcomes.

Furthermore, if the project is of reasonable length, students might be locked into a discipline-focused project that they realise does not suit them as a potential major.

To this end, a suite of self-enrolled skills modules was developed to support student skills development in a first-year, project-based engineering subject under two categories – *technical*, focusing on skills that had direct applicability to the project-work and *general*, focusing on skills related to assessment. The modules aimed to (1) improve individuals' skills in a team context; (2) give students an opportunity to learn skills unrelated to their chosen project in a low-stakes context; and (3) promote interaction and peer-learning outside of their project team and class, building a wider sense of cohort.

This paper discusses the creation of the modules and evaluates their outcomes in achieving their goals based on numerous data gathered throughout the semester and student feedback. Initial results have been positive and suggest future directions for development.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In a major review of the knowledge, skills and attributes that will be required of graduate professional engineers in the future, the “development of technical and professional skills supporting collaborative, inter-disciplinary teamwork” has been identified as becoming a more important part of the engineering education of the future [1]. In light of this, many tertiary institutions in Australia have moved to offer large-scale, first-year programmes that teach more general engineering subjects, with the aim to give students an experience of the engineering profession and begin the early development of professional skills such as problem-solving techniques and communication skills, rather than necessarily teach discipline-specific knowledge. Students commencing engineering at university often have no prior experience of engineering, what the profession entails and the distinctions between disciplines and offering general engineering subjects in this fashion can help them more broadly understand what engineering is about before committing to a particular discipline. This approach gives students some flexibility to choose or change a previously nominated engineering discipline after completion of the first year of study, without having to go back and complete discipline-specific first year subjects. This is seen as beneficial to students, especially where a broad range of engineering specialisations are offered and making a choice could become difficult.

The issue with this flexible approach is that there are several inherent concerns with pooling all engineering students into a common first-year subject, particularly one employing project-based learning [2] to help develop professional skills. Firstly, in recent years there has been a marked increase in the number of students entering the university system in Australia [1, 3]. In particular, the increase in intake means that those attending university are now coming from a wider range of backgrounds and, as a consequence, there is a greater variation in their prior knowledge and experiences [4]. The widening variance in terms of students’ knowledge, skills and past experiences, even within specific discipline areas, could lead to conflict in a team context and poor project outcomes [5]. Secondly, students who are certain about the discipline of engineering that they would like to pursue may become bored or even disillusioned if forced to complete tasks or projects in a first-year, general engineering subject that do not align with their skills and interests. These factors could easily lead to reduced educational outcomes and a negative experience of engineering, which can have dire consequences in terms of student retention.

To address these concerns, a suite of self-enrolled skills modules was developed to support student skills development in a first-year, project-based engineering subject. The modules were broadly classified under one of two categories – *technical*, focusing on skills that have direct applicability to the project-work and *general*, focusing on professional skills more related to assessment. The modules comprised a mix of self-paced online and self-signed up workshops aimed to (1) improve individuals’ skills in a team context; (2) give students an opportunity to learn skills unrelated to their chosen project in a low-stakes context; and (3) promote interaction

and peer-learning outside of their project team and class, building a wider sense of cohort.

This paper provides a background to the specific university setting and details the development and implementation of the skills modules within the context of a first-year project-based engineering subject. The relationship of the modules to each project and the assessment tasks is outlined, along with a description of the methods of delivery employed. An evaluation of the modules is performed, using numerous data gathered throughout the semester such as number of enrolments, attendance and completion rates, popularity of times when they were taken and student feedback with specific reference to the three aims mentioned above.

2 BACKGROUND

At the University of Melbourne, students must complete a three-year Bachelor of Science degree, majoring in one of the six 'Engineering Systems' majors, before choosing to apply for entry into a postgraduate Master of Engineering degree. In their first year of study, they complete the science subjects underpinning the engineering topics that they will encounter in later years of the degree – namely, mathematics, physical sciences such as physics, and possibly computing. In this context, students' first introduction to engineering is via a general first-year engineering subject – one designed for all students, irrespective of (future) discipline and intended to teach some basic discipline knowledge, introduce and develop both technical and professional skills, and provide an authentic initial experience of engineering.

The general first-year engineering subject, titled Engineering Modelling and Design, was designed from scratch as a new project-based subject, with a backbone of cohort-wide lectures supporting three independent, team projects that are delivered via smaller interactive workshop classes. The lectures were designed to be independent of choice of project and focused on the engineering profession, problem-solving methods and project management. The weekly workshop classes were three-hours in duration and consisted of one-hour of interactive teaching related to a technical part of the project and two hours of team-based project work, completing a series of incremental tasks that would build towards the final project outcome. Students complete only one out of the three possible projects over the 12-week semester in a team of three. At the beginning of the semester, each student nominated the project that they would like to complete over the semester via selecting the corresponding workshop classes in the timetable system.

3 MODULES DEVELOPMENT

The three projects were the core elements of the subject and ranged from programming an autonomous robot to designing, building and testing a speaker, to simulating and mitigating the effects of a coastal flooding event. Once the scopes, goals and content of the projects were determined, the teaching team identified any potential gaps that might exist in terms of students' prior knowledge or skills with

respect to the technical and professional skills requirements for completing each project. This process was completed through a study of the first-year students' backgrounds, observation of the current content of high school curricula and knowledge of what is covered in complementary subjects at the first-year level. These gaps were deemed sufficiently large if it was thought that they might not be able to be overcome by the students over the course of the semester without additional learning activities and support early on.

3.1 Technical skills modules

Six *technical* skills modules were developed that covered a range of discipline skills in engineering, namely Basic MATLAB/Simulink, Arduino, Robot Control in Simulink, CAD & 3D Printing, Circuit Theory and QGIS. Students would find some of these technical skills modules closely aligned with their selected project, however they were not forced to take any one particular module. Indeed, students were encouraged to take the opportunity to develop skills in areas outside of their selected project field through taking additional modules. These modules were delivered in the format of self-sign-up small-group workshop classes. During the 1.5hr facilitated workshop sessions for these modules, students would first progress through a set of guided activities to familiarise themselves with any required hardware or software. They would then be required to complete a set of specific tasks on their own in order to be certified as having completed the module.

3.2 General skills modules

Four *general* skills modules – Teamwork, Report Writing, Video Production and Prototyping – were developed. The Teamwork module was offered as self-enrolled workshops where a demonstrator would facilitate a series of team activities, including team discussion and role play. The other three modules were offered as self-paced online modules developed in H5P, comprising guided activities (that could take up to 4-5 hours) that build towards the submission of a piece of assessment. In all the four general modules, the Padlet App was utilised as a sharing and discussion platform within the activities, promoting student engagement within the cohort.

In total, there were ten skills modules available across the two categories, shown in Figure 1, along with their alignment to either project stream or assessment task. As part of the subject assessment, students were required to complete at least one General Skills module and at least one Technical Skills module to qualify for 10% of the subject mark on a pass/fail basis. The completion of a particular module was based on two components: a preparation activity and either workshop participation or submission of a piece of work. This grading scheme was chosen in order to provide a low-risk environment for students to learn additional skills, either due to the project requirements or out of interest. Under this model, even though students were 'locked' into a project at the start of semester, they would be able to explore some of the skills from the other projects in a low-risk manner.

Fig. 1. Alignment of Skills Modules with project streams and assessments

4 IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

The modules were introduced in Semester 2 2021, with a cohort of 370 students supported by 5 demonstrators. The skills modules that were supported by self-paced online activities could be completed at any time, while the workshop-based ones required students to sign up via the student Learning Management System (LMS). Enrolments were continuously monitored such that workshops could be added or removed according to demand and slots for a particular module were rotated around the week to cater for different availabilities of students.

The distribution of students completing each of the skills modules is shown in Figure 2, split according to project. It was evident that students largely preferred the technical modules most relevant to their project. Based on this data, students' perception of the technical skills modules is perhaps not to use them to explore different skills, as we might anticipate, but instead, to view them in terms of applicability to their chosen project. The Report Writing module was the most favoured general skills module, with a significantly higher completion rate compared to both the Video Production and Prototyping modules, and just ahead of Teamwork. This could be attributed to the high weighting of the report assessment in the subject (35%), and the perception of the importance of teamwork in delivering a successful project outcome. The spread of students across the three project streams for the completion of the general skills modules was relatively balanced, as we would

expect since the development of professional skills does not discriminate between the different project streams.

Fig. 2. Completion of all skills modules by project stream

Table 1 provides a summary of the completion of different combinations of the general and technical skills modules across the cohort.

Table 1. Breakdown of the number of skills modules completed

Number of modules completed		Total number of students
General module	Technical module	
0	0	36
0	1	28
0	2	5
1	0	13
1	1	265
1	2	17
1	> 2	3
2	1	3
Total		370

A majority of students (71.4%) completed the minimum requirement of one General Module and one Technical module, suggesting that most are completing only the minimum requirement to achieve the skills module component mark. A total of 22.4% did not manage to meet the minimum requirement: 9.7% did not complete either of the modules, 9.2% completed only one technical module and 3.5% completed only one general module. Only 6.2% of the cohort attempted to take on more modules than the minimum requirement.

Figure 3 shows the uptake of the skills modules that comprised of facilitated workshop sessions. Workshop attendance for the 6 technical modules and the Teamwork module appeared to be lower in Weeks 2 and 3, likely due to students adjusting to the concept of the Skills Modules at the beginning of semester.

Interestingly, there was no strong correlation between the uptake of most of the technical modules in relation to the demands of the respective project(s) at any particular timeframe during the semester, suggesting that students tend to take up the technical modules at their convenience or availability rather than during their times of need in the projects. There was however a clear ramp-up in workshop uptakes towards the end of semester as students rushed to complete the skills modules requirements by Week 11 - the week when the last of the skills modules workshop sessions were offered.

Fig. 3. Uptake of skills modules workshop sessions

A similar ramp-up trend was observed for the submissions of the self-paced online general modules, shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Submission of online task for the general skills modules

There was a significant increase in submissions during the end-of-semester SWOTvac week, particularly for the Report Writing module, attributed to the project report deadline on the first day of the exam week. The prototyping module, introduced in Week 8, being the only self-paced module that did not offer a skill that was related to the subject assessments, showed interest peaking in Week 12, implying that these students believed their project assessments were under control and had the flexibility to try something different. Approximately 9% of students managed to complete their general modules before Week 5 when the overall subject workload was not yet too demanding and the subtle spike in submissions observed during the mid-semester break week saw about 8.6% of students use this period to complete a module.

Student feedback showed that students found the general modules' materials and skills useful when applied to team assessments within the subject, however they had difficulty justifying the application of the skills to another subject as the nature of assessments were different. It was encouraging that students were particularly positive about Padlet being an effective tool for information sharing that promotes peer-learning outside of their project team and class. This was especially significant as the online self-paced had no direct interactions with peers.

For the technical skills workshop sessions, it was more difficult to achieve a balanced level of satisfaction. Students appreciated the guided activities that introduced a particular technical area facilitated by a demonstrator when a topic was new to them. However, students who have prior knowledge or experience from their project were disappointed that the workshop activities to be too basic and they are not challenged. As this is the first time the skills modules are being offered, there was only one set of activities for each technical area, with limited coverage. Despite the challenges in bridging the gap between student expectations and actual experience, students agreed that the technical modules have provided them the knowledge and application of a relevant engineering skill.

5 CONCLUSION

The skills modules were instrumental components in the subject's project-based framework that offered flexibility in terms of choice and timing in a low-risk setting. With the first-time implementation of these modules, it was found that the majority of students did not complete more than the minimum requirement of modules and, for the technical modules, largely chose them according to the perceived relevance to their project area. This is not necessarily a failure in terms of the stated goals of the skills modules but could represent the fact that most students are largely decided on which discipline of engineering they would like to pursue and accordingly pick a project aligned with that discipline and completed the most closely aligned skills module. The suite of skills modules received overall favourable student feedback and will continue to be developed into the future, including providing students with better guidance around their utility and purpose.

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